

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Faye**FIRST NAME:** Abdoulaye**PROGRAM CODE:** MBASD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Pr Laurent Cleenewerck / Dr Kabiru Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Mac

CONCEPT OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I am studying the International Academic And Professional Paper Writing courses, notably “ACA-401 Course Pack - PERIOD 1.”

The essay writing course provides detailed information on how to write clearly and to convey ideas that will support a thesis.

Furthermore, the decision to follow a particular rule of style besides being mandatory has a very positive impact against plagiarism on the way the candidates are perceived and the credit given to the findings or discovery they have made. The first step will be to strictly follow the rules of thumb and the rules of style. In this paper, based on the Euclid University Course Pack, in the first, there is information on what are the main rules that should be applied and in a second part, why it is vital to avoid plagiarism. In a nutshell, this paper is about what is a good paper.

2) A GOOD PAPER IS WELL PREPARED AND WELL STRUCTURED

A good paper is well prepared and well introduced with a question that the writer intends to answer throughout his/her demonstration.

a) A Good Paper Is Well Prepared

The preparation is critical to convey the idea that the writer would like to promote. Without a well-designed, well-planned structure, the paper can fail to address the objectives in most of the time ‘to convince’ an audience in a given domain of interest.

The prerequisite for a good academic essay is to build the knowledge that will help comprehend the subject and its implications (ACA-401 Period 1 Course Pack 2015,3) Before reading in detail the material, it is necessary to know the question I would like to provide an answer and its different terminology or nuances. The selected question guides the reader through the process of skimming and choosing relevant ideas within the material. The identification of the relevant question eases the information collection process. The question should be kept in mind during all the compilation and drafting process to avoid any deviation, irrelevancy or off-topic.

The essay plan starts with organising the ideas to get a logical flow that will support the evidence construction of my answer to the question. The plan-making needs the ideas to be put on small posters and be grouped and sorted in a way to form the initial plan. It is also essential to collect examples that will give a particular embodiment to the speech (ACA-401 Period 1 Course Pack 2015,2). However, this is not enough; it should be kept clear what is the instruction when they have been provided as per the exact terms used to define the question.

Paragraphs are the building block of an essay. They should contain topic statements that are essential as they are the main idea of the paragraph, and this first statement can be in the beginning part of the paragraph. The topic sentence is followed by supporting sentences, evidence and examples.

Besides the structure, another crucial dimension of academic writing is to pick up the right rule of style to the domain.

The rule of style is the selected markers to deliver strong signals to get recognition of peers either from the same circles or different areas of research. Lawyers and economists are not using the same writing set and can easily be exposed, thanks to the way they write and hence the way they resonate.

b) A Good Paper Is Well Structured

Paragraphs of the body are the building blocks of a research paper that is preceded by an introduction and sealed by the conclusion. The strongly organised structure of paragraphs is paramount to demonstrate an excellent master of the body of knowledge. The paragraphs should follow a consistent stream. The structural elements complemented with relevant examples and well-documented citations allow sustaining the arguments with a solid basis. The initial plan will change as the drafting advances. Reiteration is the usual and expected process of an essay. Once the study plan is set, then the drafting and writing stage should start promptly.

Each paragraph should include one central idea, sentences, supporting evidence and examples. Evidence should be sourced, analysed and interpreted with clear statements on the repercussion, importance and effect. A critical conclusion based on the evidence should conclude the paragraph (ACA-401 Period 1 Course Pack 2015, 4).

Once the plan set, to work on writing the first draft as early as possible to avoid any more extended stress. However, the first draft is not the outcome, and as per the plan, it will need several refinements before being satisfactory. Many iterations of work on the documents are necessary to make sure that it will get to the expected standards. The best friend of a writer is the time that will help in to mature the ideas. The essay is at the drafting work in progress, which can have many flaws at the beginning. The writer does not have to be concerned too much and has to correct the flaws gradually. Once completed with the preparation, there is still a need to perform some proofreading and to ensure that all parts of the essays are fine-structured and contains well delineate introduction, body and conclusion. It is essential to ascertain that all the expression used to convey the ideas and positions. Finally check the transition signals and punctuation to make sure that the reader follows well the arguments and is not lost (ACA-401 Period 1 Course Pack 2015 , 4). It is also vital to ensure that the text is united and coherent. In a paragraph, all ideas should relate to the topic sentence.

Once the final version is ready to be handed to the lecturer, it is necessary to ensure that it meets the format of the delivery and send it as per required to the exact recipients. The late delivery will mean to lose marks. Before handing in the paper, one has to follow a checklist and make sure to have thoroughly answered the whole question. It is paramount to ascertain that all materials used from other sources and paraphrases are well cited. Finally made the counts of the words ensure that they remain within the set word limit (ACA-401 Period 1 Course Pack 2015, 5).

3) STYLE WITHOUT PLAGIARISM

The use of guided style can prevent plagiarism by providing some tips of quoting and citing whenever the idea is from another source.

c) A Good Paper Contains Right Set of Style

A good paper includes the right set of style that is suitable for the domain. A lawyer is expected to use the Bluebook. The same specifiers of styles go for the health specialists who can make proper usage of the WHO rule of style. Therefore, the rule of style is a marker of identity.

The academic writing style is formal unless instructed as per the Euclid Coursepack in respect to the response papers where the use of personal pronouns like 'I' and 'me' for example are accepted and should avoid contracted word such as "don't" and be in plain English as much as possible. However, some Latin expressions can be tolerated for example when an original 'misused' word has been accurately quoted, the Latin term '(sic)' is used to emphasise the term and signal to the reader that the word is cited faithfully. The aim of using plain English is to provide the full clarity and to avoid any misunderstanding

while not being clumsy, patronising and pompous (ACA-401 Period 1 Course Pack 2015, 43).

The Euclid Course Pack for the first period includes a separate guide that explains the Chicago Manual of Style (author/date system) and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, and Dissertations, 1996 (published by the University of Chicago Press), this is merely the Chicago style applied to research papers — revised Fall 2006. The guide explains the rules related to abbreviations, capitalisation, compound words, italics & quotation marks, numbers, quotations as well as the Chicago page formats and Chicago endnotes & footnotes (ACA-401 Period 1 Course Pack 2015, 66–77).

Furthermore, there are notable differences between British English and American English, and the writer should always pay attention to choose a language and not to diverge from it while staying coherent.

Hence, the habit of using the correct referencing style using the correct tools will ease the reference-making and prevents the writer from plagiarism.

d) A Good Paper Avoid Plagiarism

The avoidance of giving credit is unethical and a serious academic offence. Plagiarism occurs in an essay when using material without using quotation marks or a footnote/in-text citation.

Referencing is the method of recognising the sources used when writing the paper using the Course Pack and two excellent videos on understanding templates and styles from the course ACA-401 (Euclid University ACA-401 Vimeo Video 2016) and the referencing tool introduced by the Zotero video tutorial. The two videos will teach the operators to use the tools and ensure familiarity with the referencing style required by Euclid University. Euclid University recommends the use of Zotero as a reference management tool, its templates for response /major papers and the Turabian rule of style for its response and major papers.

Research supports the provision of different ideas, and citation or quotation systematically provide credit to authors while the text is not originally yours and when essential to be mentioned and referred back. However, quotations must be added only when needed and to support the thesis.

Paraphrase, statistic/data, or graphs, when borrowed from another source, are circumstances that impose citing the sources. Paraphrases are to be used in the terms the information that an author has produced the knowledge, which another author has created. When not too close, the paraphrase is a useful tool when used scrupulously to avoid too many quotes. Furthermore, it is not always advised to cite everything; it is not needed to cite when the thing is common sense or very widespread. It is also permitted not to cite during the supervised examinations (ACA-401 Period 1 Course Pack 2015, 38). However, giving credit to the authors, especially when they are well known, and the phrase is,

historical, for example for the “Veni Vidi Vici” of Julius Caesar. Furthermore, Euclid University recommends making two or three citations during the midterm exam.

4) CONCLUSION

What does a good essay needs? The dissertation aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence, and it should answer a question with the use of the right set of style. An academic paper being formal should stay away from any temptation of plagiarism and citing the relevant sources. Reference, supporting evidence and examples are essential to the claim of academic texts. Using the tools taught by the Euclid University Course Pack is the first step to write a good academic essay. My takeaway is that the writing process is not at one go; it is a process that needs several refinements before getting to the desired outcome.

REFERENCES

Euclid. 2015. ACA-401 Course Pack-PERIOD 1. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.